

The Effect Of Implementing Artificial Intelligence On Job Performance In Commercial Banks Of Jordan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: March 09, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: June 06, 2024</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Artificial Intelligence; Job Performance and Commercial Banks of Jordan, Experience Systems (ES), Neural Networks (NN), Genetic Algorithms (GA), Intelligences Agents (IA).</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11507493</p>	<p><i>This Research paper aimed to clarify the effect of AI with its variables (ES, NN, GA, and IA) on job performance. The banking sector in Jordan is used as a study community and targeted managers at all levels, and in order to achieve the objectives of the study. Design/Methodology/Approach: The sample consisted of (319) managers. Also, the study used the descriptive approach and the data are analyzed on SPSS.</i></p> <p><i>Research findings: The results showed that there is a statistically significant effect of artificial intelligence that effects on job performance through (GA, and IA) only. In addition, the results showed that gender, academic qualification and years of experience have a statistically significant effect on job performance in commercial banks in Jordan. The study recommends preparing future research for the same variables and the study community, but for another country, in order to generalize the results.</i></p>

Introduction

Many organizations around the world are heavily relying on artificial intelligence techniques to employee performance, develop their capabilities and empower them. This would enhance the attractiveness of the work environment in these institutions and make them a destination for competencies and those with expertise and skills. However, there are some prominent challenges facing such institutions when adopting artificial intelligence technologies. First, the challenge of employee engagement and integration in the work environment. Second, the limited number of experts and specialists in the field of artificial intelligence. Third, employees' lack of acceptance of change and their fear of shifting towards smart technology Federal Authority for Governmental Human Resources (FAGHR, 2019).

The problem of this study focuses on the fact that most of the employees in the banking sector need continuous improvement and development to reach the strategic objectives of the organization. However, it is extremely difficult for some organizations to obtain competent employees due to the scarcity of the competent human element. Therefore, organizations resort to expert systems, artificial intelligence systems and smart agents not only raise the efficiency and effectiveness of the employees, but also improve their performance to reach the desired goals. So, in light of the above, the study problem can be formulated in the following questions:

- What is the extent of the expert systems, neural networks, genetic algorithms, and intelligent agents' contribution in improving the employees' performance in commercial banks of Jordan?
- Is there a correlation to the effect of artificial intelligence with its variables (neural networks, genetic algorithms, and intelligent agents) in improving employees' performance?
- Does job performance among the employees in the banking sector differ by (gender - educational qualification - years of experience)?

The study tries to reach the following goals. Firstly, identifying the obstacles which the artificial intelligence implementation in commercial banks of Jordan is facing. Secondly, clarifying the concept of artificial intelligence and job performance, its management systems and its various models for both higher management and workers; hence be adopted. Thirdly, achieving the correlation between the theoretical and academic concepts that have been put forward and the possibility of applying them in the field. Fourthly, determining the level of impact between the two variables of the study. Finally, defining the management that the one of the fundamental reasons for the development of the banking sector is concern for both issues.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, very few studies have addressed The Effect of Implementing Artificial Intelligence on Job Performance in Commercial Banks of Jordan. Commitment has been researched within Job Performance, Especially with regard to organizations' performance systems. Also, this construct (Artificial intelligence) has also been applied to decision-making in business supports (Al-Jaber, 2020; Frank, Author, Bessen, Brynjolfsson, Cebrian, Deming and Wang, 2019 and Ajjam, 2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

One of the oldest challenges facing humanity is the urgent need to find solutions that can simplify life. After changing hard physical labor to automatic machines, society thought of creating machines capable of performing (mental) work, which for a long time had been a purely human privilege (Bikeev, Kabanov, Begishev and Khisamova, 2019). Artificial intelligence (AI) may replace human capital in performing some tasks, such as adaptive tasks and contextual and organizational performance. These tasks are increasingly being replaced with artificial intelligence. At the same time, other tasks not shown historically as tasks are transformed for several parts of the HR workflow. So, they can be performed using AI tools (Agrawal, Gans and Goldfarb, 2019).

Therefrom, AI technologies have already begun to affect the human resources and job performance in organizations by building detailed monitoring, training and developing plans for each employee's performance based on background processes. These processes rely on big data or data analytics related to the employee's practices in real time (Alhashmi, Salloum and Abdallah, 2019). And with the emergence of new technologies, the organizations have already started to see creative use cases of artificial intelligence in ways that can bring more positive benefits to workflows. This is according to a review by Infor, a leader in the supply of applications for industry-specific and cloud-based companies, the impact of artificial intelligence technologies on the performance of employees in job performance departments (Acemoglu, and Pascual, 2019).

Only five years ago, the examples mentioned above were probably pure fiction. However, with the advent of innovative text analysis algorithms and pioneering classification methodologies in the fields of machine learning as well as the maturity of big data analytics, AI technologies are poised to revolutionize in job performance with unimaginable way (Sayidy, 2018).

Job performance is one of the important vital processes that are very reliable in judging the extent of the success of institutions and organizations in reaching their goals and achieving their plans in the short and long terms. That is, a concept that links between the aspects of activity and the goals that organizations seek to achieve through the tasks and duties of the workers. Therefore, job performance is the process by which officials realize the level of an individual's performance of his/her tasks, abilities to accomplish and the characteristics necessary to perform work efficiently (Joseph, 2014). Some companies, with appropriate internal technologies, have built their own artificial intelligence technology which allows them to customize programs according to their specific goals and culture. For example, Infor, which specializes in developing business application solutions with cloud computing about integrating the Infor Coleman platform for artificial intelligence, was specifically designed for companies with the Infor Talent Science HR app. This one helps the career-based profiles (Taman, 2017).

The Federal Authority for Government Human Resources has recently organized a "Webinar" session for the Human Resources Club. This session indicated that artificial intelligence has greatly contributed to enhancing the efficiency of the job performance system in institutions and companies, as these companies now use many systems and applications of artificial intelligence. The ability to assess the competence of candidates for their vacant jobs enhances the ability of these institutions to recruit the most efficient talent. It also allows the possibility of tracking employment indicators in real time (FAGHR, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence (AI):

The successive developments in computer science and its software during the last twenty years have been of great speed; outperforming other developments in other sciences. One of the great and recent developments in software is the so-called AI, which is one of the modern technologies.

AI techniques have made a great revolution in the field of information technology because AI is an important sector of computer science. AI includes the innovation of smart gadgets and programs that function like human (Kamble and Shah, 2018); it is "a name mostly used to refer to science and which aims to provide students with the ability to perform functions such as reasoning, planning, learning and perception." Moreover, AI is designed to raise the capabilities of workers, not replace them, as it makes connections between complex applications, workers, computers, knowledge, and the physical world. One of its capabilities is to enable applications during their work to distribute and retrieve data, data mining, product design, manufacturing, and scheduling. However, AI systems depend on human experiences and knowledge; therefore, AI systems choose logical models. The current systems are an extension of human experiences, but they do not replace them because they lack human feeling (Shaw, Rudzicz, Jamieson and Goldfarb, 2019).

Artificial Intelligence is computer science that is concerned with creating and studying computer systems that display a form of intelligence. In other words, it is "systems that learn new concepts and tasks, think and draw

conclusions." This requires human intelligence. Besides that, AI means studying the ideas that will form machines capable of simulation in line with traditional human responses by looking at the human capacity for intention, thinking and conclusion (Shukla and Vijay, 2013).

Tuomi (2018) defines AI as "a machine that understands and interprets sounds and languages, works to solve problems, can diagnose medical cases, control cars on the roads, play games like chess, and imitate impressionistic images from Van Gogh paintings." By definition, artificial intelligence is "a system that has the ability to perform tasks normally associated with living organisms". Also, AlSedrah (2017) defines AI as the field which depicts the basic learning skill just like humans, and examines the ability to respond to some behaviors."

The rapid advancement in AI and automation technologies has the potential to wreak havoc on labour markets. Both of AI and automation are able to increase the productivity of some workers and replace some work done by others and potentially transform nearly all occupations at least to some extent (Frank et al., 2019).

Consequently, the importance of AI lies in its use as a method similar to the human method in solving complex problems characterized by synchronization, accuracy and high speed in receiving and addressing hypotheses, and the ability to find a solution to each problem, as well as the ability to process non-digital data of a symbolic nature. "It is also difficult to prepare, as it requires the representation of huge amounts of knowledge in specific fields, and among its objectives is to simulate a person in his way of thinking, behaviors or response, and to create new, creative and innovative ideas (Simin, Malekian, Alizadeh, Taheri and Ashouri, 2013).

Independence and prediction are the ability of AI to work independently. The systems of AI are able to perform very complicated tasks, such as driving a car without the need for human's control or supervision. There are some tremendous possibilities about the economic challenges and disruptions in the labor market which are observed by the applications of AI, and its possible effect in the future (Al-Jaber, 2020).

Artificial Intelligence is important in monitoring. The risks which arise because of the independence of AI include both predictability problems and control problems. Humans may face difficulties in maintaining control of the programmed devices. There are many problems that occurs as a priority causing loss of control. First, a malfunction, such as a damaged coil or physical damage of the device. Second, security breach. Here, the large response from these applications appear with a superior response time compared to humans. If AI is designed with a feature, it will enable AI to learn and adapt. That what makes AI a potential source of public risk on a scale far beyond the familiar forms which arise solely from human behaviors (Scherer, 2016).

Artificial intelligence has played a prominent role in improving the employee's life cycle in the organization, changed the prevailing traditional concepts and methods of engaging employees, and enabled institutions to survey employees' opinions and visions on various topics and issues of interest to them in the work environment. It is also important to point out that modern technology and artificial intelligence technologies have become an integral part of the work system of institutions wishing to keep pace with the developments and rapid changes in the world.

AI Dimensions

1- Experience Systems (ES)

Experience Systems are considered one of the applications of AI programs. The family refers to a variety of current and new applications in different global and theoretical fields, and therefore, the nature of this family is open and receive new members and innovations associated with previously unknown uses of artificial intelligence technology. In particular technologies integrated with information systems in the organization.

Experience Systems are "techniques that discover solutions to problems that require specialized knowledge and skill, and the system operates in them by the expert's thinking, skills and motivations in order to simulate them." So, ES techniques are different types of AI methods, in which the parameters of functionality are recorded (Mazaryazdi and Soleimani, 2010). It is possible to develop ES program for any problem that involves choosing from a specific set of options, as functionality depends on logical steps. Hence, any area in which Person A or Group possesses special expertise that others need is a potential area of ES (Chukwu, 2018). Also, ES can use their knowledge base in order to achieve decisions and tasks in a way that meets the organization's goal (Frank et al., 2019).

Neural Networks (NN)

Also called artificial neural networks. NN attempt to mimic the human brain actions. NN are a system of devices or programs that are designed in the shape of neurons in the human brain. It is a variety of deep learning technology which falls under the family of intelligence Artificial.

Neural Networks are defined by some researchers who believe that NN depend in their work on a simple view of the nerves. These nerves are arranged in levels forming a large network, and the network's function is determined by both learning and communication (Kenji, 2013). In the same context, others see NN as a process of processing information in a manner similar to the human nervous system, and the main thing is the different structuring of the information processing system by processing large amounts of unconnected information to

solve special problems. Thus, the neurons will change the strength of the interconnections between the elements of the processes in response to changing patterns in the received data and the results achieved (Yaris & Ahmad, 2014).

Neural Networks have the property of learning and deriving meanings from complex data, developing complex models and trends that are difficult to observe, whether by humans or ordinary computers. NN provide us with multiple projects by giving answers to questions (Shaw et al., 2019). In addition, commercial applications of these technologies generally focus on solving complex signals, processing problems or recognize patterns in job performance. Examples of significant commercial applications since 2000 are handwriting recognition for check processing, speech-to-text transcription, oil exploration data analysis, weather forecasting and facial pattern recognition (Atom, 2019).

Genetic Algorithms (GA)

An algorithm is the set of repeated instructions which are used to solve a problem. The word genetic refers to the behaviour of algorithms that can resemble biological processes. It is also inspired by Darwin's theory of natural selection to solve optimization problems; especially with complete or incomplete information, or even limited computational ability (Kumar, 2018).

O'Brien (2000) defines GA as solving methods that help find solutions to specific problems using methods suitable with their environment. According to Ajjam (2018) GA are programmed to work in the way humans solve problems by changing and reorganizing component parts using methods such as reproduction, transformation, and natural selection, thus providing us with methods to search for all possible combinations of numbers to identify the correct non-numeric variables that represent the best possible structure for a problem. These methods are useful in situations where thousands of solutions are possible and must be evaluated to produce an optimal solution.

Genetic Algorithms are a growing application of AI that are used in mathematical applications to simulate advanced procedures which produce better solutions to the problem. Therefore, GA are used in various sciences, technologies, and business processes. GA is also a system that tries to find the mix of inputs that give the best results. It is also suitable for making decisions in environments with hundreds of solutions. The potential that it finds and evaluates with multiple capabilities is faster than a human (Baltzan and Phillips, 2008).

Intelligences Agents (IA)

Intelligences Agents are an object that can perceive the environment in which it is present through the sensors that this object possesses and then respond to it by means of the actuator or prey mechanisms. Figure 1 shows the relationship of the agent to his environment. It is a knowledge-based ES implanted within information systems that are dependent on the computer or its components to make it smarter. Moreover, it is an end-user program or method for carrying out events (Petropoulos, 2018). IA is the knowledge base stored in it about a specific person or process to make decisions and accomplish tasks in a way that achieves the user's goals. Also, AI is anything that observes its environment through sensors and actuates by responding to the environment, and is therefore a design with a program.

In addition, Shaw et al., (2019) remind that AI is software applications that help in keeping the company's internet tasks related to buying and selling, and it warns users when something important happens. Today, there are many AI applications in operating systems such as software applications, email systems, and cell phone programs. Microsoft Office programs contain programs that help the user in creating files, drawing diagrams, and providing assistance when needed. One of these programs is wizard, including the journey within the internet to search for data and information.

The Job Performance

Job performance represents a special place within any organization that is considered the final product of the outcome of all activities in it at the level of the individual, the organization and the state. As a result, the organization is more stable and longer lasting where the performance of employees is distinguished, and that the attention of the organization's management and its leadership are usually in the level of performance. It exceeds the interest of workers in it.

There have been many definitions of the concept of job performance as it refers to the degree of achievement and completion of the tasks that make up the job of the individual. Job performance reflects how the individual achieves or satisfies the requirements of the job. However, there are often confusion and overlap between performance and effort. Effort refers to the energy expended, while performance is measured on the basis of the results achieved by the individual (Pradhan and Jena, 2017).

The performance is what the employees do in their work according to the goals of the organization. It is a measurable (observable) behaviour. They are also physical, activities and psychological activities, such as cognitive processes and problem solving (Ramdani et al., 2019). In addition, the researchers also emphasize that job performance is a behaviour rather than outcomes. The behavior is consistent with organizational goals and is multidimensional. There are three components of performance: understanding and knowledge of work tasks,

knowledge, skills and abilities and more specific knowledge about the procedures for performing the tasks. Third, motivation (Koopmans, Bernaards, Hildebrandt, Vet, De and Beek, 2012).

The concept of performance overlaps with some other concepts which will try to draw the boundaries of these concepts, so that it can be distinguished. Some of these concepts are effectiveness, efficiency and productivity. Through these previous definitions, job performance represents the means by which the individual satisfies the requirements of the job it performs. Firstly, performance is the summary of the employee's accomplishment of his/her assigned tasks. Secondly, it is the process of converting all incentives, experiences, competence and awareness into outputs, which is the completion of tasks without errors and with the required quality. Thirdly, it is the result of the interaction between motivation, effort, experience and competence. Finally, it can be said that it is a behaviour directed towards achieving the goals of the organization (Muda, Rafiki and Harahap, 2014).

Hence, the definition of job performance can be deduced as the employees' implementation of the tasks and duties required to achieve the goals and responsibilities of the organization in accordance with the provisions of the laws and organizational decrees. These are specified for each job and its duties, and which are finally achieved by integrating them and grouping the objectives together of the organization. This is done effectively and efficiently. Taking into consideration the time needed to accomplish the job.

Accordingly, it can be said that job performance is of great importance to the organizations because any organizational level within the organization or in any part of it is not a reflection of the capabilities and motivations of heads and leaders. But the importance of job performance from the organization's point of view is due to its connection to its life cycle in its various stages of dissolution, namely: the stage of survival and continuity, the stage of stability, the stage of reputation and pride, the stage of distinction, the stage of leadership, and then the ability of the organization to skip a stage of growth and enter a more advanced stage depending on its levels of functional performance (Farhi, 2017).

In his study, Kharshi (2019) emphasized the effectiveness of the job performance of human resources management and its role in achieving distinguished performance on the importance of the organization's job performance. This is because job performance has effectiveness in achieving the goals set by the organization regardless of the costs entailed by these goals. The efficiency of the organization through the optimum utilization of available resources at the lowest cost is the ratio between outputs and inputs as well as between the results obtained and the means used. That is "a relative relationship between the elements of production used to generate a certain amount of production (goods and services) and the value of production according to a specific monetary or physical scale."

Elements of Job Performance (JP)

According to (Farhi, 2017; Kharshi, 2019), the job performance in an organization that has basic elements or components through which it can measure and determine the level of the employee's performance are:

The employee and his competencies: They are what the employee has in terms of knowledge, skills, interests, values, trends and motives. On the other hand, his competencies mean what the employee has in terms of information, skills, trends and values that represent the basic characteristics which produce an effective performance by that employee. In addition to dedication, seriousness in work, the ability to assume responsibilities and complete work on time and the extent of the need for supervision and direction.

Work and its requirements: that include the tasks, responsibilities, roles, skills and experiences required by the job and its requirements and challenges. They also include accuracy, order, mastery, ingenuity, technical mastery, ability to organize and implement work, speed of achievement and freedom from errors.

The organizational environment and its components: that consist of internal and external factors. The internal factors affect the performance and include the organization, its structure, objectives, resource, strategic position and the procedures used. As for the external factors, which are the economic, social, technological, cultural factors, political and legal. These form the environment of organization that affects effective performance.

Knowledge of job requirements: that includes general knowledge, technical skills and professional background about the job and related fields.

Quality of work: It is represented in the extent to which the individual is aware of the work he is doing, the desire, skills, ingenuity and ability to organize and implement the work without falling into risks.

The Number of tasks is completed: that an employee can accomplish in normal work conditions as well as the amount of speed of this achievement.

The organizational environment and its components: that consists of internal and external factors. The internal factors that affect the performance and include the organization, its structure, objectives, resource, strategic position and the procedures used. As for the external factors that form the environment of organization that affect effective performance, they are the economic, social, technological, and cultural factors, Political and legal.

Knowledge of job requirements: that includes general knowledge, technical skills, and professional background about the job and related fields.

Quality of work: It is represented in the extent to which the individual is aware of the work he is doing, the desire, skills, ingenuity and ability to organize and implement the work without falling into risks.

The Number of tasks is completed: that an employee can accomplish in normal work conditions, and the amount of speed of this achievement.

PREVIOUS STUDIES

1- The Al-Jaber's study (2020), entitled "The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Efficiency of Computational Growth in Jordanian Banks,"The study aimed to identify the impact of artificial intelligence on the efficiency of accounting systems in Jordanian banks, the population of the study was (16) banks. Random sample included (129) questionnaires were analysed by the subject to statistical analysis. The results showed the presence of the effect of using artificial intelligence on the efficiency of accounting systems in Jordanian banks. The study reached several recommendations including the need to enhance the use of artificial intelligence in the bank to raise the bank's efficiency. In addition, the management of Jordanian banks should assist expert systems in acquiring knowledge from the knowledge bases stored in the systems in many areas that support the capabilities of the higher management.

2- The Frank et al.'s study (2019) entitled " Toward understanding the impact of artificial intelligence on labor".The study aimed to discuss barriers that prevent scientists from measuring the impacts of AI and automation on the future of work. These barriers include a lack of high-quality data about the nature of work (the dynamic requirements of professions), for the key processes at the micro level (skill substitution and human-machine integration) and an insufficient understanding of how cognitive technologies interact. With broader economic dynamics and institutional mechanisms (such as urban migration, international trade policy). Overcoming these barriers will require improvements in the temporal and spatial accuracy of the data as well as improvements in data related to workplace skills. These improvements will enable the study to quantitatively monitor and predict the complex evolution of work alongside technological advances. Finally, given the underlying uncertainties in predicting technological change. This paper recommends the development of a decision framework that focuses on resilience in the face of unforeseen scenarios as well as overall equilibrium performance.

3-The Ajjam's Study (2018), entitled "Artificial Intelligence and its Implications for High-Performance Organizations".It aimed to find out artificial intelligence and its impact on high-performance organizations. The Ministry of Science and Technology was the population chosen to conduct the study and distribute (40) questionnaires. After analyzing the data, the results showed that there is an effect of artificial intelligence on the work of the ministry. The study presented a set of recommendations. The most important of which was the need to expand the applications of artificial intelligence according to the needs of the departments for each type of artificial intelligence in order to advance the reality of the ministry to a better level.

4- The Ramdani et al.'s study (2019) entitled, " The individual work performance scale: A psychometric study and its application for employee performance ". This aimed to get an individual work performance scale of the modified version which is more acceptable and has a good psychometric property. The participants in this study were campus faculty who were selected using targeted sampling techniques. The samples participating in this study were 303 participants. The Individual Work Performance Scale has a comprehensive methodology and good psychometric properties. A descriptive approach was used to analyze the data. The revised version of the Individual Work Performance Scale (IWP) has good psychometric strength seen by its high reliability coefficient, the fit model of the structure it builds, and the validity standards in terms of structure and exterior. Therefore, it is highly recommended that the revised version of the IWP be used in the evaluation and evaluation of an employee's work performance in general, and especially in an academic environment.

5- The Kharshi'sstudy (2019), entitled " The effectiveness of the job performance of human resources management and its role in achieving distinguished performance".It aimed to find out the contribution of the effectiveness of job performance in achieving the distinguished performance of individuals in the human resource department of sports institution. This field study was applied in the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Wilayat of M'sila. The study sample consisted of 30 employees from the Directorate of Youth and Sports in the Wilayat of M'sila. The study reached several results. The most important of which is that individual capabilities have a role in achieving the distinguished performance of individuals for managing the human resources of the sports institution. The study recommended working on developing a job performance evaluation system to contribute effectively to the process of administrative development by developing the criteria for the job performance evaluation system, as these criteria focus on aspects related to job performance levels.

Methodology

The Study Design and Sampling

The study used the descriptive and analytical approach due to its compatibility with the nature of the current research. The population consisted of (319) managers working in 16 Jordanian commercial banks in Amman. Table 1. shows the distribution of the sample members according to personal variables.

Table 1. Distribution of the sample members as the gender variable

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	183	57.4
	Female	136	42.6
Total		319	100%
Academic Qualification	Diploma		
	Bachelor	258	80.9
	M.A.	61	19.1
	PhD		
Total		319	100%
Years of Experience	5 years or less	38	11.9
	From 10 to 15 years	185	58.0
	From 16 to 20 years	96	30.1
Total		319	100%

Table 1. shows the characteristics of the study sample that is depending on the gender variable. Males are the most frequent reaching (183), at a percentage of (57.4%), while females are the least frequent reaching (136) and with a percentage of (42.6%).

Depending on the level of academic qualification variable, the employees who hold a bachelor's degree are the most frequent reaching (258) with a percentage of (80.9%), while employees with a master's degree are the least frequent reaching (61) and with a percentage of (19.1%).

Depending on Years of Experience variable, the employees who have (10-15 years) experience are the most frequent reaching (185) with a percentage of (58%), while the employees who have (5 years or less) experience are the least frequent reaching (38) with a percentage of (11.9%).

To analyses the data and answer the study questions, the five-point Likert scale is relied on to answer the questions according to the degree shown in table 2. That is to interpret the arithmetic means of the respondents' responses in each statement of the questionnaire and in each of study areas

Table 2. Likert scale

Degree	1	2	3	4	5
Approval level	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Not Agree	Strongly Disagree

As for the levels of approval degree, which this study adopted when commenting on the arithmetic mean of the variables included in the study form. They are three levels (high, moderate, low) based on the following equation: Length of the period = (the highest for the alternative - the lowest for the alternative) / of levels, $(1-5) / 3 = 4/3 = 1.33$, so the levels are as follows (Sekaran, 2011).

Approval rating a low from -1 to less than 2.33. a moderate approval score of 2.33 - less than 3.66. and the approval score is a high from 3.66-5.

In addition, the statistical methods are used in analyzing the collected data, within the (SPSS v.23) program to describe the characteristics of the respondents by using frequencies and and percentages. Moreover, a group of inferential statistics methods are used to answer the study questions, namely - the Cronbach Alpha equation, arithmetic means and standard deviations.

The Study Variables

The study includes two variables, the first is the independent variable of (AI) which includes four independent sub-variables are (ES), (NN), (GA), and (IA). The second is the dependent variable, which is job performance (JP) (Ajjam, 2018; Bikeev et al., 2019; Alhashmi et al., 2019). Figure 1 depicts the conceptual model of this research.

Figure1. Research Model

According to the research model, the one main hypothesis and four sub hypotheses have been formulated as the following:

- **H01:** There is a statistically significant effect of **AI** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan.
- **H01.1:** There is a statistically effect of **ES** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan.
- **H01.2:** There is a statistically effect of **NN** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan.
- **H01.3:** There is a statistically effect of **GA** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan.
- **H01.4:** There is a statistically significant effect of **IA** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan.

The Study Tool

After reviewing previous studies and theoretical literature, a questionnaire was developed to measure the effect of artificial intelligence on job performance of the individuals of the research sample. The research tool consisted of two areas: the first: Artificial Intelligence which consisted of (16) statements and divided into four sub-dimensions.

In order to ensure the stability of the study tool, the tool stability equation (Cronbach Alpha) is applied for all fields of study, see table 3.

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the fields of study

No.	The Field of Study	Number of statements	Cronbach's alpha
1.	ES	4	0.67
2.	NN	4	0.74
3.	GA	4	0.69
4.	IA	4	0.71
5.	JP	8	0.80
Total		24	0.86

Table 3. shows the Cronbach alpha coefficients for the study fields ranged between (0.67-0.80). The highest is in the field of “job performance” and the lowest is in the field of “Experience systems (ES)”. The Cronbach alpha coefficient for the questionnaire as a whole reached (0.86). And all the stability coefficients are high and acceptable for the purposes of the study. However, the stability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) is acceptable if it exceeds (0.60).

THE RESEARCH RESULTS

This part includes a detailed presentation of the statistical analysis for the study' results, it aims to identify the effect of artificial intelligence on the job performance in commercial banks of Jordan, as well as depending on the study questions.

Results related of answering the first and second question: The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the questionnaire axes are calculated (ES), (NN), (GA), and (IA). Then, the main hypothesis of the study and the sub hypotheses are analyzed to find out the extent which these dimensions contribute to improving the job performance between the workers in commercial banks of Jordan, as follows:

First: The arithmetic means and standard deviations for the questionnaire axes.

Table 4. The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the questionnaire axes.

No.	Statement	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	Rank	Level of importance
1	ES	3.92	.29	1	High
4	IA	3.86	.35	2	High
5	JP	3.84	.45	3	High
3	GA	3.83	.29	4	High
2	NN	1.92	.24	5	Low
Total		3.47	.22	Moderate	

Table 4. shows that arithmetic means of the questionnaire axes as a whole was (3.47) and a standard deviation was (0.22) with a moderate level of importance, as the arithmetic means ranged between (1.92 - 3.92). Whereas the ES are the first rank with an arithmetic mean (3.92) and a high level, the IA are the second rank with an arithmetic mean (3.86) and a high level. The JP are in the third rank with an arithmetic mean (3.84) and a high level. The GA are in the fourth rank with an arithmetic mean (3.83) and a high level. Finally, the NN are in the last rank with an arithmetic mean (1.92) and a low level of importance.

Second: Analysis of study hypotheses.: Main hypothesis: To find out the effect of artificial intelligence with its variables on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan. Multiple regression analysis is used, see Table 5.

Table 5. Multiple regression analysis to find out the effect of artificial intelligence on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan

Independent variable	Coefficient β	T	Sig.*t	R	R ²	F	F Sig*	Constant Coefficient
ES	0.012	0.311	0.756	0.796	0.634	7.135	.000	-1.75
NN	0.012	0.308	0.758					
GA	0.289	7.08	0.000					
IA	0.769	21.14	0.000					

The results of the statistical analysis in Table 5. show a statistically significant effect of artificial intelligence with its variables on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan. The correlation coefficient is R (0.796) at a significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). As for the determination coefficient, R², reaching (0.634). Meaning that AI with its variables explains 63.4% of the changes in job performance in commercial banks of Jordan. This confirms the correct of the null hypothesis which is: "**H01: There is a statistically significant effect of AI on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan**".

In addition, Table 5. shows the results of the statistical analysis of the sub-hypotheses as following: **The first sub-hypothesis.** There is no statistical effect of **ES** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan, as the T value reaching (0.311) and statistically significant (0.756), which is no significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). While **the second sub-hypothesis.** There is no statistical effect of **NN** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan as the T value reaching (0.308) and statistically significant (0.758), which is not significant at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$).

The third sub-hypothesis. There is a statistical effect of **GA** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan. The significance of this effect is confirmed by the T value is (7.08) and in statistical significance (0.00), which is a function at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). β (0.289). This means that an increase of one degree in the level of genetic algorithms leads to an increase in the level of job performance in commercial banks of Jordan with a value of (0.289). Finally, **the fourth sub-hypothesis.** There is a statistical effect of **IA** on job performance in commercial banks of Jordan. The significance of this effect is confirmed by the value of T (21.14) and in statistical significance (0.00), which is a function of the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.05$). β (0.769). This means that an increase of one degree in the level of intelligent agents (IA) leads to an increase in the level of job performance in commercial banks of Jordan with a value of (0.769).

The results of answering the third question. The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the competence of workers in the banking sector were calculated according to the variables of gender, academic qualification and years of experience. The application of a T-test for independent samples and a test of variance analysis "F" to determine the differences between the arithmetic means was used. See Table 6.

Table 6.A T-test of samples and a single-test analysis

Variables	Category	Frequency	Arithmetic means	Standard deviations	T. test	
Gender	Male	183	3.54	.18	T=7.05	.000
	Female	136	3.38	.23		
Academic Qualification	Diploma	0			T= -2.61	.009
	Bachelor	258	3.46	.23		
	M.A.	61	3.54	.17		
	PhD	0				
Years of Experience	5 years or less	38	3.43	.27	F=25.85	.000
	From 10 to 15 years	185	3.42	.20		
	From 16 to 20 years	96	3.60	.17		

Table 6. shows a T-test for independent samples and a single-test analysis of variance to find differences in job performance among the employees in banks according to gender, academic qualification and years of experience. The results showed the following:

- 1- There are statistically significant differences in job performance among the employees in the banking

sector according to the gender variable. The value of T reached (7.05) and in statistical terms (0.00), which is a statistical indication. This means that males perform better.

- 2- The existence of statistically significant differences in job performance among the employees in banks according to the academic qualification, as the value of T (-2.61) and in statistical significance (0.009), which is a statistically significant one. This means that those with an academic qualification are the best performance. The existence of statistically significant differences in job performance among the employees in banks according to years of experience, where the value of F is (25.85) and in statistical terms (0.00), which is a statistically significant one. This means that the owners of years of experience (16-20 years) are the best performance.

DISCUSSION

After collecting and analyzing data, the above results are emerged, where the level of importance of artificial intelligence in commercial banks in Jordan. The results showed that the level of importance of artificial intelligence in job performance is moderate. This is because the management in the bank does not rely on neural networks in processing its data or in deriving data. It also does not have multiple options in performance. Besides, the databases that have neural networks are devoid of artificial intelligence. In addition, banks do not have expert systems on which to rely on functional performance and thinking processes because they rely on computer systems of medium complexity.

Moreover, the results showed the validity of the main hypothesis, as artificial intelligence affects job performance through GA, and IA. This is because banks rely on GA in their performance to find smart solutions and non-digital issues, and help the managers to reach performance results quickly. These GA are constantly being developed in the changing environment. On the other hand, IA affects the job performance by helping bank managers to make administrative decisions within a stored database. Those managers use IA as an alternative to human agents in order to reduce the cost of transactions and help to reduce the time used to reach the desired goal. This means that the more interest is in artificial intelligence through GA, and IA, the more efficient is the level of job performance in commercial banks in Jordan.

But on the other hand, the results showed that ES and NN do not affect the job performance in commercial banks in Jordan. Despite the fact that the high level of management interest in both dimensions; ES and NN, by technological development used in banks, they do not affect job performance.

As for the sample of the study, the results found that commercial banks in Jordan depend more on males in their management than females, and that the academic qualification (masters) is sufficient in performing the required job tasks. Also, years of experience from 10 to 20 years are necessary to raise performance efficiency. This indicates that gender, academic qualification, and years of experience heavily affect job performance among employees in commercial banks in Jordan. This is done through, first, the ability to overcome the difficulties encountered while working at the bank. Second, the Knowledge of the fundamentals and concepts which are related to work in the bank. Third, the knowledge of the bank's systems and procedures. Fourth, the following up of developments in the field of work in the bank. Finally, the possibility of assuming higher responsibilities within the job at the bank. Thus, a stronger and more powerful functional performance.

Conclusion

Summary

This study aimed to know the effect of artificial intelligence with its variables (ES, NN, GA, and IA) on job performance. The study used previous literature and published research in order to build a model that demonstrates this effect. It used artificial intelligence as an independent dimension and job performance as a dependent dimension. Then the hypotheses and questions of the study are constructed. In addition, the study developed a scale to collect data and know the opinions of managers in banks to reach the objectives of the study. After analysing the data, results confirmed the validity of the hypotheses imposed by the study; therefore, and the study questions were answered.

This study concluded that artificial intelligence directly affects job performance through (GA, and IA) only, and within certain conditions and specific experiences that characterize managers in the bank. Also, the interest in artificial intelligence increases the bank's efficiency and strengthens its ability to perform banking internally and externally.

Suggestion

The study recommends that researchers should work on future studies for the same variables and the study community. This should be applied in another country to generalize the results and reach measures that raise the job performance of the banking sector.

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